

Green consumer behavior in an emerging economy: confusion, credibility, and compatibility

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Abstract

Purpose – The purpose of this research is to contribute to a better understanding of deeper motivations and inhibitors of green consumer behavior in the context of emerging economies.

Based on the findings, it aims to provide implications for marketers and policy making.

Design/methodology/approach – Based on an ethnographic approach, in-depth interviews and observational data were used to study 15 Mexican families from four urban regions of Mexico with different incomes. Thematic analysis was used to develop and validate themes and codes.

Findings – The findings highlight three dominant themes related to uncertainty in the adoption of environmentally-friendly behaviors: consumer confusion, trust and credibility, and compatibility. Overall, green behaviors seem to be ingrained in the traditional heritage of savings and frugality rather than based on strong environmental values. It is suggested that the factors that drive consumers from positive attitudes and intentions to the actual adoption of green behaviors are a combination of perceived personal benefits, decreased perceived risk and uncertainty, a sense of control over costs, and a decomposition and reconstruction of deeply embedded cultural values and practices.

Practical implications – Policy makers and marketers are advised to build on collaborative efforts in order to facilitate comprehension and adoption of environmentally-friendly behaviors and green

products. In order to construct modernity alongside environmental responsibility, it seems indispensable to provide affordable lower-priced alternatives for the low-income segments of the market which constitute the vast majority of the population in emerging economies.

Originality/value – Being one of very few available qualitative studies on green consumer behavior, this study delves into the tension between modernity and traditional heritage in the context of emerging economies.

Keywords

Green consumer behavior, Ecocentric perspective, Ethnography, Thematic analysis, Mexico, Consumer behaviour, Emerging markets.

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Introduction

The process of deterioration of natural resources caused by human beings increases the importance of the responsible role of every player, such as consumers, governments, institutions, companies, and the media, in the environmental crisis. Since the 1975 UNESCO Conference in Belgrade, the necessity of having a population that is motivated, educated, and prepared to take care of the environment has been acknowledged (UNESCO, 1977). That idea has been reinforced at the United Nations Conference (1992) in Rio de Janeiro in Brazil at the signing of the Kyoto Protocol (1997) and at the United Nations Conference (2010) in Quintana Roo, Mexico (see an overview of UN decisions on climate change UNFCCC, 2011). Nevertheless, the anthropocentric paradigm, along with the partisan interests of the governments, has hindered the attainment of major commitments to protect the planet. The anthropocentric paradigm is based on the assumption that there is a clear and morally relevant dividing line between human beings and the rest of nature (Purser *et al.*, 1995). The ecocentric paradigm in turn focuses on sustainability and emphasizes the value of nature independently from the benefits it provides for human beings (Iyer, 1999). Purser *et al.* (1995) explained that “ecocentric seeks to affect change at the level of human values, ethics, attitudes, and lifestyles. Ecocentric values are aligned with movements to preserve wilderness areas, protect the integrity of biotic communities, and restore ecosystems to a healthy state of equilibrium” (p. 1069).

In order to advance towards an authentic ecocentric worldview, a better understanding of the conducts of acquisition and disposition of the individual resources is necessary. Understanding the motivators and inhibitors of green consumer behavior is a prerequisite for formulating and designing incentives and stimuli that are able to effectively change these behaviors. This paper intends to address the problem from a qualitative perspective in order to identify underlying motivations and meanings behind green consumer behavior in the context of an emerging economy, such as Mexico. We selected Mexico, a country with a population of 113 million and a gross domestic product of around USD 13,000 per capita in 2011 (Central Intelligence Agency, 2011) because along with other Latin American countries such as Brazil, Argentina and Chile, it presents important challenges due to a positive economic growth and important social and technological changes. Urbanization has brought numerous environmental demands in developing countries. It is critical for firms, which are attempting to compete based on green appeals, to understand and

adequately meet the needs of consumers in these regions. The theoretical framework for this article is based on three pillars. The first pillar relates to the conceptualization of environmentally responsible behavior. The second dimension captures the factors that affect green consumer behavior, and the third-dimension comments on consumer resistance of green behaviors. This framework serves as a platform into which the results of our empirical study will be integrated. Subsequent section describes the methodology of the study, including the sample characteristics and techniques for data analysis. Finally, the results of the study are shown and discussed, and avenues for future research are proposed.

Conceptualization of environmentally responsible behavior

Research on environmentally responsible behavior has used various terms interchangeably, such as environmental behavior, green behavior, ecological behavior, environmentally friendly behavior, and sustainable behavior. However, it remains unclear whether these expressions are mere synonyms or nuances between them that should be considered in theory development and practical applications. Based on the premise that the conceptualization of an object of study depends on its historical timing, Corral-Verdugo and Pinheiro (2004) suggested that environmental terms should be analyzed according to the historical moment when the concepts arise. They suggested that pro-environmental and ecologically friendly behaviors gained wide use from the middle 1980s to the late 1990s. The latter period is characterized by increased solid waste and the ever-widening concern of governments regarding environmental deterioration, which led to the publication of important strategic papers, e.g. the report of the World Commission on Environment and Development (1987). In this context, environmental behavior and ecologically responsible behavior involve actions undertaken by a person, either individually or in a collective scenario, in favor of the conservation of natural resources and with the intention to obtain a better environmental quality (De Castro, 2001). Pro-environmental behavior is also defined as the group of deliberate actions in response to social and individual requirements that originate from the protection of the environment (Corral-Verdugo, 2001, p. 37). These definitions emphasize the protection of the environment in face of conservationist social requirements. Notwithstanding, Corral-Verdugo and Pinheiro (2004) criticized that pro-environmental behaviors tend to preserve only the physical environment without expressing explicit interest in the human welfare and related aspects, such as social and economic justice or the benefits of health, employment, and education. Since the late 1990s, the concept of sustainable behavior, defined as a set of effective, deliberate, and preemptive actions that lead to the preservation of natural resources, including the integrity of animal and plant life, as well as the individual and social welfare of current and future human generations replaced the terms of pro-environmental, pro-ecological, or

simply environmental behavior (Corral-Verdugo and Pinheiro, 2004, p. 10). This concept, which utilizes an integral approach compared to the previous ones, involves individual and group actions aimed at the rational use of natural resources, guaranteeing the welfare of individuals as well as ecologic equilibrium. It includes energy savings and water, compost preparation, ecological building, and birth control since they favor high levels of welfare in the economic, political, environmental, and social domains. Interestingly, from this perspective, recycling is not seen as providing a high environmental benefit since it requires power and water and generates pollution in the re-conversion process. Concerning the reduction of consumption, when such reduction is extreme, it has a negative influence on the economic level since it affects employment for many people who depend on the elaboration of products and their distribution as a means of survival. In this paper, we will refer to these environmentally friendly or sustainable behaviors as “green behaviors”.

Another ordering scheme of environment-protecting actions involves the so-called 3R's, reducing, reusing, and recycling (compare, e.g. Inami, 2001). In this hierarchical taxonomy, reduction refers to minimizing or eliminating the amount of materials of single use or to reducing the use of power or resources. Reusing suggests the idea of giving a second useful life to an object while recycling alludes to the application of a process to materials in order for them to be used again. Our research takes up the perspective of the 3R's, but includes a fourth pillar, that is, the purchase of items labeled as ecological/biological/organic products. From our standpoint, this perspective allows for the analysis of concrete sustainable consumption behaviors and actions by defining actions favorable to the preservation of the environment in clear-cut terms.

Factors that affect green consumer behavior

Factors that have been shown to exert influence on the ecological behavior of individuals have been generally classified as external (e.g. education, media, family, or culture), internal (e.g. knowledge, attitudes, awareness, or involvement), and situational (economic rewards and legislation). Other researches have focused on demographic and psychographic criteria to explain green consumer behavior. These studies will be reviewed in more detail in the following paragraphs, with the aim to compare findings in developed countries vs. emerging countries.

Green consumer determinants

The 1990s experienced a substantial increase in the number of studies on green behavior determinants. However, these efforts have focused on developed rather than on emerging economies. For example, Diamantopoulos *et al.* (2003) reported

that most studies have been conducted in the USA, Australia, Germany, France, Denmark, and the UK. Regarding empirical research conducted in developed economies, one finding emphasizes the significance of attitudes in predicting ecological behaviors. Even though some studies found only a weak attitude-behavior relationship (e.g. D'íaz Meneses and Beerli Palacio, 2006; Kollmuss and Agyeman, 2002), most studies demonstrated the existence of strong relationship (e.g. Bei and Simpson, 1995; Hamzaoui and Zahaf, 2009; Gatersleben *et al.*, 2002; Laroche *et al.*, 2002; Mainieri *et al.*, 1997; Schlegelmilch *et al.*, 1996).

For example, a study conducted in the USA (Bei and Simpson, 1995) suggested that consumers who believe in a greater utility of their purchases are more likely to buy recycled products. Specifically, positive attitudes toward recycled products, the feeling of contribution to the environment from the purchase of recycled products, believed quality (belief that the recycled products were superior to the ordinary ones in quality), and expected price difference related positively to consumers' acquisition of recycled products. Another study conducted by Mainieri *et al.* (1997) in the US showed that specific consumer beliefs and general environmental attitudes significantly predicted green buying behaviors. In Holland, Gatersleben *et al.* (2002) found that environmental awareness had a positive influence on the acquisition of environmentally conscious food products and recycling. Investigating the relationship among knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors in Canada, Laroche *et al.* (2002) observed that although most relationships were either weak or non-significant, there were two strong associations between two attitudes (importance and inconvenience of being environmentally friendly) and two intention behavior variables (willingness to pay more for green products and recycling). More recently, Hamzaoui and Zahaf (2009) explored Canadian consumers' motivations to purchase organic food. Using a qualitative approach, they found that environmental, health, and benefits concerns related to organic food demand.

Concerning studies in emerging economies, consumers seem to express little environmental commitment. Chan's (1999) study conducted in China provided evidence for the effect of attitude on the limited ecological behavior of adult consumers. Through the analysis of the relationship between cognitive, affective, and behavioral components of ecological attitudes and behaviors, the author demonstrated that primarily a limited knowledge of this subject, the costs of environmentally-friendly products, and the low perceived credibility of environmental claims related to green products affect the reduced commitment of the Chinese regarding the environment. On the other hand, Lee's (2008) research with adolescents from Hong Kong showed that social influence (peer network), environmental concern, concern with self- image in environmental protection, and perceived effectiveness of

environmental behavior are the most important predictors of consumers' green purchasing behavior. Contrary to Chan's previous study (1999), environmental attitudes ranked as least important.

Ger's (1999) qualitative study with consumers from different social strata in Turkey revealed that they assign a reduced importance to the protection of the environment. Even when most consumers possess knowledge of environmental problems, they generally do not consider the environmental effect of their daily practices. Their concerns are oriented more towards cleanliness and aesthetics rather than the protection of resources. Some low-impact ecological practices, such as the use of pressure cookers, the metro, and recycling, have become deeply rooted, but they are not based on environmental awareness. Rather, these behaviors are associated with modernity, westernization, progress, and fun. Reusing package material signals, for example, creativity and sometimes status when a prestigious brand name is visible on the packages or the bag. A similar orientation towards modernity has been observed in a recent study by Schafer *et al.* (2011) on consumption habits, home equipment, and transportation in an urban area of Southern Brazil. The authors found that the intensive use of electronics, household devices, and private cars is limited more by the financial restrictions of many consumers rather than by an authentic ecological awareness.

Considering last examples of factors linked to green behaviors in emerging economies, we shall put forward the cases of Greece and India. In a study on the consumption of ecological food in Greece, Fotopoulos and Krystallis (2002) provided evidence for low levels of organic food purchases by Greek consumers despite their high awareness of this subject. They further reported that habits and price perception influence the consumption of organic products. Regarding India, price considerations seem to increase decisional conflict in consumers. Manaktola and Jauhari (2007) indicated a significant relationship between the Indian consumers' attitudes and their behavior towards green practices in the hotel industry. Indian consumers with a positive attitude towards hotels who have adopted green practices seem to patronize these practices but are not willing to pay extra for them. That is, consumers' awareness of the benefits of environmental practices in hotels does not translate to a greater disposition to pay more.

Green consumer segments

Research on green marketing has attempted to profile green consumer segments using various variables. These include socio-demographic characteristics (Buttel and Taylor, 1992; Carson and Moulden, 1991; Diamantopoulos *et al.*, 2003; Scott and Willits, 1994; Stern *et al.*, 1995; Straughan and Roberts, 1999), psychographic measures (Do Paco and Raposo, 2008; Gilg *et al.*, 2005; Steel, 1996) and geographic variables

(Tremblay and Dunlap, 1978). Whereas the majority of these studies were conducted in developed regions of Europe and the USA, very little is known about consumers in emerging and less developed economies, such as Mexico.

Socio-demographic characteristics. Traditional research on profiling green consumers seems to indicate that age and education are two of the most important variables predicting environmental behavior (Buttel and Taylor, 1992). The general belief is that younger individuals are likely to be more sensitive to environmental issues. The argument is that those consumers who have grown up in a time in which environmental concerns have been a salient issue are more likely to be open to these issues (Straughan and Roberts, 1999). On the other hand, education is expected to correlate positively with environmental concerns and behavior (Straughan and Roberts, 1999). Consumers with higher levels of education are more aware of the environmental issues; hence, are more concerned about environmental quality and more motivated to participate in environmentally responsible behaviors (Diamantopoulos *et al.*, 2003). Income is another socioeconomic variable generally thought to be related to environmental sensitivity. The common justification for this belief is that individuals at higher income levels can bear the marginal increase in costs associated with supporting green causes and favoring green product offerings (Straughan and Roberts, 1999). Moreover, higher social classes are more likely to witness the effects of degradation of the natural environment through their outdoor leisure pursuits (Diamantopoulos *et al.*, 2003).

However, most studies appear to indicate a limited or ambiguous value of socio-demographic characteristics in segmenting green consumers (e.g. Scott and Willits, 1994; Stern *et al.*, 1995). The main reason is that socio-demographic variables can be used, at least to some degree, to profile consumers in terms of environmental knowledge and attitudes; however, they are of limited use when the behavioral aspects of environmental consciousness components are concerned (Diamantopoulos *et al.*, 2003). Further, country-specific factors may partly explain current findings on differences in environmentally friendly behavior. For example, the speed and types of legislative change in the environmental area differ largely by country. Carson and Moulden (1991) identified that environmental requirements are generally much stricter in developed countries than in emerging economies. Thus, a possible explanation is that environmental consciousness is a function of situational characteristics rather than socio-demographic measures. For example, it may be argued that emerging economies with substantial environmental problems, such as air pollution, contamination of water supplies, and detrimental effects of infrastructure development, are more likely to be knowledgeable and feel strongly about such issues and, consequently, are more likely to campaign against their effects.

Psychographic measures. Research on environmental actions has examined the effect of underlying values on behavior. It has been found that high levels of environmental activism are strongly linked to values that consider the natural environment to be of great importance in a person's life (Steel, 1996). Green consumers tend to hold not only more pro-environmental, but also more pro-social values. Specifically, committed environmentalists value wealth, personal influence, and power less than they do unity and other aspects of altruism. Further, committed environmentalists are more likely to hold biospheric and ecocentric values and to emphasize the need to work with the environment, rather than relying on technological solutions (Gilg *et al.*, 2005). A study conducted with Portuguese consumers showed that despite their support for policies designed to improve the environment, these consumers do not translate their concerns into actions since they rarely join environmentalist associations, and they do not take part in policymaking. Their participation is often based on protecting the environment by saving electricity and water, which shows that these concerns may be more closely related to economic factors than to environmental consciousness (Do Paco and Raposo, 2008).

Geographic measures. It is generally assumed that rural and urban residents are exposed to different levels of environmental pollution and thus hold different attitudes toward the natural environment. Thus, researchers usually expect to find a relationship between residence and environmental quality concerns. Several studies showed that residence relates to pollution concerns, with urban residents being more concerned about pollution compared to rural residents. This is why researchers argue that the rural-urban dichotomy is a relatively important variable in sociological analysis (Tremblay and Dunlap, 1978). In a more recent study, Kalantari and Asadi (2010) showed that urban residents of an emerging economy, such as Tehran, are willing to dedicate their time to participate in pro-environmental activities, but they believe that money for environmental protection should come from the government. This study also revealed that urban Tehran residents do not consider the environment, when compared with other social and economic issues, a relevant problem yet. An important implication from the study is that increased environmental knowledge, in combination with more environmental information and an increased awareness of people about the consequences of environmental problems, may lead to increased feelings of stress. Heightened levels of environmentally induced stress in turn affect environmental attitudes and behaviors of urban residents in emerging economies. In addition, preparedness to act and environmental legislations also seem to play an important role in changing environmental behavior in these types of economies.

Consumer resistance towards green consumer behaviors

As demonstrated in the preceding sections of this article, previous research on green consumer behavior has focused on non-consumption behaviors aimed at reducing resource and energy use (Gardner and Stern, 2002). These so-called curtailment behaviors include water and energy conservation, car use reduction, and to some extent, recycling and responsible waste disposal. One important characteristic of these behaviors is that they usually do not cost extra; however, they require frequent efforts and often result in discomfort for the individual performing the behavior. Moreover, these behaviors are associated with changing habits and are usually difficult to implement from a policy perspective (Gardner and Abraham, 2007). The second category of green behaviors is often referred to as energy efficiency increasing behaviors or technology choices (Stern, 2000). They are called technology choices since they often involve substituting old inefficient technology for more efficient solutions. In a recent study, Jansson *et al.* (2010) found that values, beliefs, norms, and habit strength contribute to explaining low-involvement curtailment behaviors as well as high involvement (eco-innovation) adoption. The values most strongly associated with green behaviors are social-altruistic (decisions to act green that are based on the perceived costs and benefits for other people) and biospheric (decisions to act green that are based on the perceived costs and benefits for the ecosystem/biosphere). Meanwhile, egoistic values (decisions to act green that are based on the perceived costs and benefits for the individual) indicate that people will act green only if they perceive that individual benefits exceed the costs (Hansla *et al.*, 2008). In conjunction with values, different types of beliefs are found to affect green consumer behavior. It has been found that a pro-environmental norm with a high potential to affect actual behavior develops if a person is aware of the environmental consequences of a behavior and ascribes responsibility to them for taking preventive actions (Jansson *et al.*, 2010).

The benefits from adoption (i.e. a change in environmental behavior) need to have personal relevance for potential adopters in order to take action. Personal relevance can, however, trigger emotional reactions and thus change perceptions and attitudes. Further, strong social norms are needed to encourage adoption, because without social norms, people cannot judge whether adopting a new behavior is accepted or not. Overall, a combination of perceived personal benefits as a consequence of signing up to a green tariff; compatibility with individuals' values, identity, and social references; strong social influence and normative beliefs; a sense of control over costs and associated inconveniences attached to switching over; good information and no perceived risk or uncertainty push people from "intention to adopt" to "actual adoption" (Ozaki, 2011). Particularly in the context of emerging economies, it is noteworthy to emphasize the strong and direct effect of perceived uncertainty on the intention to adopt new products. In this sense, Ibarra *et al.* (2010) found evidence that

the associated risks and uncertainties of Mexican consumers towards new technologies could be important barriers for adoption. Thus, identifying consumers' uncertainties towards adopting green products should become a relevant goal for companies and organizations in these markets.

Methodology

An ethnographic approach was followed in order to collect empirical data for this study. This methodology offers a contextual understanding of the aspects that determine the green consumer behavior. This study examined 15 Mexican families from different social classes living in three regions, Central (Mexico City and Toluca), West (Guadalajara), and North Mexico (Monterrey). Social class was estimated on the grounds of a personal judgment based on indicators such as living place, size and type of dwelling, consumer durables, education, and expressions and language used by family members. Congruent with the qualitative research paradigm, a theoretical, purposive sampling approach (Glaser and Strauss, 1967; Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Wallendorf and Belk, 1989) was used.

The ethnographic techniques used to collect data consisted of participant observation and interviews. The former took place while families were engaged in particular activities in and outside their homes. These activities included, e.g. house cleaning, meal preparation, eating, after-meal cleaning, social reunions, and grocery shopping. Following Goetz and LeCompte (1988), the objective was to contemplate family activities, listen to conversations, and interact with family members in order to obtain relevant data on re-using, recycling, reducing, and acquiring ecological products. In order to avoid intentional manipulation of the variables of the study, families were told that the research was on purchase behavior and consumption in general. Questions referring to ecological consumption were presented later on during interviews. Along with participant observation, photos were taken as evidence of both ecological and anti-ecological behaviors, such as using of compact fluorescent lamps (CFL), purchasing of ecological products, and saving water while washing dishes, among others. These observations thus allowed triangulating data from observation, interviews, and informal conversations.

Interviews followed the techniques recommended by McCracken (1988). Whenever possible, researchers sought to conduct separate interviews with each family member as well as at least one interview with the family gathered during a habitual family event, such as lunch or dinner. Further, in some instances, families were accompanied on their shopping trips to local retailers. Queries with family members had the intention to seek what they knew, thought, and felt about the influence of other stakeholders, such as media, business organizations, government, and other external

stakeholders. Additional, socio-demographic aspects along with their personal stories helped explain their behaviors.

To prepare data for analysis, all interviews were transcribed and compiled with observation notes. Next, thematic analysis (Boyatzis, 1998) followed three distinguished phases: sample and subsample selection, development of themes and codes, and coding validation. For sample analysis, three families with very high levels of environmental behavior (subsample A) and three with very low environmental behavior (subsample B) were selected. This analysis helped identify preliminary themes and codes within each one of the two subsamples. Theme and code development followed an iterative process from empirical data (data-driven code). Next, codes were compared between subsamples. For instance, motivator codes identified for families with high ecological behaviors were contrasted with inhibitor codes for families with low ecological behaviors. Such contrasts created maximum differences between subsamples. Codes required to be non-episodic and included the following: name, definition, and examples in order to eliminate any confusion during analysis. Next, coding reliability (inter-coder consistency) was determined. It has been proposed that reliability from a qualitative perspective is attained by comparing codes from the analyses of individual researchers (Boyatzis, 1998). Therefore, the concurring codes were then defined as (preliminarily) valid while the conflicting ones were revised according to the empirical data. Before moving to the last phase of coding validation, codes were applied to the rest of the case studies conducted with the remaining nine families. Finally, a qualitative code validation was implemented. That is, families with high ecological behavior (Sample A) were compared to families with low ecological behavior (Sample B) in terms of codes. The codes that differed between groups were selected as valid codes. In addition, we compared codes in order to condense codes into more meaningful constructs and finally into interpretive layers of themes (Arnould and Wallendorf, 1994). These themes are presented in the next section. We translated verbatim quotations from Spanish transcripts into English, seeking to adhere to the exact wording of the quotations without altering their meaning. In order to protect the privacy of our respondents, we substituted their real names with common Mexican names.

Results: emerging themes in green consumption behavior

Independently of social class and geographical region, Mexican consumers did not show high levels of environmentally friendly behavior. For example, members from poorer families did not recycle less compared to members from richer families. Moreover, families from the northern part of Mexico (which is presumably influenced to a higher extent by a western, American-type lifestyle) did not buy a greater amount of organic food compared to their counterparts from the South. Out of the four

ecologically friendly behaviors, those related to reducing and re-using were observed more frequently among the families in our sample. On the other hand, environmentally friendly practices related to recycling and purchasing organic products were less common. When it comes to reducing, Mexican households frequently strive to save energy and water, although these behaviors are often based on economic considerations rather than the desire to improve the natural environment. Behaviors related to re-use include, e.g. the re-use of plastic bags obtained at retail outlets, refilling plastic bottles, or the retention of cardboard boxes to be reused by other family members.

The results of this study confirm that the family is at the center of Mexican households, and our findings suggest that the overwhelming amount of environmentally-related behaviors is determined by the importance of the family. The well-being of the family, a much more concrete and tangible entity than the abstract notion of society (*Gesellschaft*), seems to be more important than anything else, and protecting the natural environment can be conceptualized as an instrumental goal serving to accomplish the terminal goal of securing the integration and well-being of the family. We thus conclude that anthropocentric worldview dominates environmentally friendly behaviors across all social classes. In the following sections, we present three themes that emerged from the analysis of the 15 cases in our study: consumer confusion, credibility, and compatibility.

Consumer confusion: generational differences Consumer confusion has become an important and persistent issue for marketing practitioners (Mitchell and Papavassiliou, 1999) and generated substantial problems in the domain of green marketing. For example, Chrysochoidis (2000) demonstrated that consumers frequently struggle to differentiate between organic and conventional food. Our research confirms relatively high levels of consumer confusion among our respondents, which sometimes translates into a general skepticism towards environmental claims. For example, to our respondents, the exact meanings of eco-labels, such as fair trade, no genetic engineering, sustainable agriculture, sustainable wood, or animal welfare, are not always clear. This prevalence of confusion towards environmental topics was persistent across all social classes, as exemplified by the following excerpts from our ethnographic interviews.

The important thing is to understand why a product is ecological and how this product is good for us, and why we should buy it [..] sometimes it is difficult to understand [..] [Natalia, 37, Novo Family, Monterrey, Middle Class].

Green products should be better [..] don't they? But I do not really know why [..] [Flora, 50, Blanco Family, Mexico City, Higher Class].

Green products are the ones that can make you save money [. . .] although sometimes people say that these products are more expensive [. . .] The truth is that I do not really know [. . .] [Pedro, 36, Perez Family, Monterrey, Lower Class].

As these verbalizations exemplify, consumer confusion is caused either by an absence of information, as in the case of Flora, or by the co-existence of contradictory information, as in the case of Pedro. One important reason for this consumer confusion may be the lack of information provided by companies and the government. By not understanding abstract labels, such as sustainable agriculture, consumers are apparently unable to assign a clear benefit to these products and thus they fail to incorporate these criteria into their decision-making. By providing more tangible and relevant information, consumers might better understand how organic milk is different from “conventional” milk or how cows from sustainable agriculture are kept under conditions that affect positively the cow’s health and the quality of their milk, and how avoiding over-fertilization preserves the natural environment.

When analyzing consumer’s consciousness related to the natural environment by age, we found that children have usually more environmental knowledge and higher levels of involvement with environmental protection compared to their parents. Regardless of social class, children in our study were more active in reducing, re-using, and recycling, and they also demanded these behaviors from adults, thus acting as agents of change. This finding is congruent with the results from Easterling *et al.* (1995) who proposed that children may become catalysts for family environmental consumerism and that their concern for the environment is based on their cognitive status, their exposure to nature, and their contact with particular socializing influences. Our study suggests that school, where knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to the natural environment are formed, has an important socializing influence for children. In a sort of bottom-up socialization, parents are subsequently influenced by their children and persuaded to show a more positive environmental behavior.

It is my daughter who tells me, look at that or at school they tell her what that to do with the garbage, so she influences a lot with helping me or telling me things one doesn’t know [Diana, 30, Delgado Family, Toluca, Lower Class].

We celebrate “Earth Day” at school and we think about actions to give a break to the planet. We think of the planet as if it was a person – although it cannot speak to us, it has feelings [Sebastian, 11, Blanco Family, Mexico City, Higher Class].

These examples show that education in school is an important element in the socialization of children, which influences positively the development of knowledge and attitudes required to induce behavioral changes. Adults are usually not exposed to this kind of socialization agents, and even if they were, they would probably be less

receptive to new information because it is usually easier to develop attitudes and behaviors from scratch as opposed to changing existing ones. Children also seem to have a more holistic worldview of the environment in contrast to adults, and often mention environmental behaviors not only as a means to increase the well-being of the immediate family, but also as a means to improve conditions for all human beings, animals, and the planet in general. Thus, compared to adults, children are more likely to internalize the concept of solidarity as a necessary condition in order to shift from an anthropocentric to an ecocentric worldview, as expressed in the following explanation by a ten-year old, middle-class girl.

Well, I think that there is no care in Mexico because they don't care for the trees, they don't care if older or younger girls live in a world where they almost can't breathe [.. .] When I walked on the street, I asked my grandma, "Grandma, don't they have a consciousness about themselves? Don't they even think in their children, don't they care? Or be it that they die and live in heaven [.. .] They do not care for anything, what it costs them doing it when it rains, a raindrop among everyone would be more than 1,900 raindrops that could be recycled" [.. .] [Carmen, 10, Chavez Family, Mexico City, Middle Class].

Whereas school has some success as a socialization agent, most of our informants felt that the government should take a more active role when it comes to environmental development in the population. Specifically, respondents felt that the government should, for example, provide the necessary infrastructure to promote public transportation or separate waste, implement stricter environmental regulations, and facilitate clear information about environmental matters.

The government should educate people to respect our environment [.. .] It should create organizations, legislations [.. .] [Guillermo, 48, Gomez Family, Toluca, Middle Class].

The government should explain us how we could save energy [.. .] how to separate garbage [Diana, 25, Lopez Family, Monterrey, Lower Class].

Trust, credibility, and consumer resistance

Similar to the findings from Mendleson and Polonsky (1995), many of our informants perceive environmental products and claims not only as confusing, but also as deceptive. Specifically, they seem to feel that producers and retailers act only in the self-interest of higher profit margins, and that the media are the covert allies of these companies. Generally speaking, the level of trust related to environmental products appears to be low, and individuals do not show much interest in investigating whether environmental claims are true or not. The attitudes of our informants ranged from mild skepticism towards environmental claims to the deeply held conviction that companies and the mass media lie about green products.

The problem with these [green] companies is that, I am not sure if I should believe them or not [Martha, 50, Martinez Family, Monterrey, Higher Class].

We don't know if we should trust [them] [...]. On TV, even cookies talk! So you should not believe everything they say [Pedro, 36, Perez Family, Monterrey, Lower Class].

Much of what they [the companies] say about being ecological is just to disguise [...] in reality it is not true [Nicola's, 40, Novo Family, Monterrey, Middle Class].

What they say are sheer lies [referring to the communication in the mass media about green products] [Diana, 25, Lo'pez Family, Monterrey, Lower Class].

For me, sometimes these are just fairy tales in order to ask for more money [...]. [Nicolas, 40, Novo Family, Monterrey, Middle Class].

According to Ottman (2011), industry gets blamed these days of greenwashing practices (when a company/product misleads consumers by making a false green claim). This could be due to the antecedents of industry being responsible for polluting the water, land, and air, and because consumers do not have adequate information about environmental issues.

For example, we noticed that our respondents do not have information about the product's level of greenness and about solid facts regarding its green benefits. Individuals also tend to believe that their actions cannot have a significant effect on the planet (Prakash, 2002). A need to develop transparent industry standards and certification processes, such as third-party verification of green business practices that would validate the claims made by a company, was evident among our respondents.

We need to know that they [the green products] are certified and that they really deliver what they are promising. Because these products claim that they have certain attributes and perhaps they do not [Guillermo, 48, Gomez Family, Toluca, Middle Class].

Consumer trust should be fostered allowing marketers of green products to build a congruent message to consumers so they will perceive a reliable product and will have a positive attitude towards it. We found that this lack of trust is not directed solely towards industry, but extends to government institutions and may even lead to active consumer resistance. For example, families justify that they do not separate waste because the local administration does not offer separate waste collection.

When the garbage truck comes, the operators mix everything – there's no point in it [Bernardo, 17, Blanco Family, Mexico City, High Class].

In the school buildings there are bins for garbage separation [...] the problem is that later, everything will be mixed and it doesn't work [...] [Diana, 25, Lo'pez Family,

Monterrey, Lower Class].

Although our respondents thought that environmentally responsible behavior is everybody's duty, they argued that the role of government institutions is crucial for policy formulation. Establishing a coherent regulatory and institutional framework could thus increase consumers' trust and credibility.

The government definitely influences in our behavior because it's them who many times determine through laws why we live in a rule of law, what is prohibited or allowed [...] although we don't want it, it exists [...] [Guillermo, 48, Gomez Family, Toluca, Middle Class].

Compatibility: savings, practical utility, habits, and modernity

Although a substantial number of our informants showed some environmentally friendly behavior, a traditional emphasis on savings and frugality rather than on strong environmental values motivated this conduct. As evidenced in the previous sections of this article, the environmental consciousness of the Mexican consumer remains fragile and intermittent. It is thus not surprising that Mexican consumers practice green consumption with an emphasis on economic savings rather than on a concern for the natural environment.

We collect paper and plastic bottles in order to receive some extra money [Elena, 31, Espinoza's Family, Toluca, Low Class].

Saving money is indeed a main driver of environmentally- friendly behavior for the lower classes. Because saving electric energy and water or recycling aluminum cans, paper, glass, and PET presents an important means for the lower classes in Mexico to not only save economic resources, as in the case of reducing the use of energy and water, but also to obtain some extra income, as in the case of recycling. Therefore, most family members participate in these practices. However, in many cases, family members are largely unaware of the precise implications of their behavior on the natural environment. Although it might be argued that the motivation behind a specific action is of interest as long as the action is taken, these preeminent knowledge gaps will become relevant the moment these relatively poor strata of the society can improve their economic situation and when saving money ceases to be the main reason for their energy-saving and pro-recycling behavior. On the other hand, families from higher social classes also save energy, though based on different motivations. However, the economic crisis also affects the disposable income and the psychological state of more affluent consumers in Mexico, with the result that people from the higher middle and even the higher classes strive to protect their incomes. While saving money is an important factor in the reduction of energy consumption, it also plays a major role in purchasing organic products, but in reversed

form. That is, economic considerations are a motivator in reducing and re-using behaviors but an inhibitor when it comes to buying green or environmentally friendly products. Thus, it is not surprising that especially the lower classes are not interested in green or ecologically friendly products. Generally, families that buy green products generally come from higher social classes, but even for them this is not a common practice due to the economic uncertainty in the country combined with a fragmented awareness of environmental problems.

The finding that the majority of families we interviewed seem to search for practical utility of the products they consume provides further evidence for the lack of environmental consciousness. For example, all of our informants reported using disposable cups and plates during social gatherings, and this behavior is clearly convenience-based. Less effort is needed to place used plates and cups in the garbage than to wash the dishes. Further, disposable dishes are less likely to break compared to conventional ones made of ceramics or glass. The orientation of Mexican consumers towards convenience is further reflected in relatively limited recycling efforts. Separating glass or plastic is associated with additional non-monetary costs, such as time and physical effort. Disconnecting electronic devices or walking instead of using one's own car represents a sacrifice, which many consumers are not willing to accept. Consequently, we argue that consumers are willing to engage in environmentally friendly behavior only when the economic benefit is perceived as being higher than the non-monetary costs. Our finding that the lower social classes are in general more prone to recycle compared to the higher social classes thus can be explained by the fact that the monetary benefit and the non-monetary costs of recycling form a greater positive balance, which is not the case for a more affluent person. Specifically, the utility from receiving 20 pesos for recycling aluminum cans would be substantially higher for a poor than for a rich family, and thus the difference between the monetary benefit and the non-monetary cost may be positive for the former and negative for the latter.

In analyzing more deeply the environmental behaviors of our respondents, beneath the obvious layer of tangible and rational arguments, we identified a second layer of explanations related to deeply-rooted habits and traditions which may either be in favor or in opposition to environmentally-friendly behaviors. The use of disposable dishes at family reunions is a typical example of a habit that is never really questioned. As one of our interview partner explained,

It is a routine to buy disposable dishes for gatherings. At the supermarket we don't search for new products – we buy things on a routine basis [Martha, 50, Martinez's Family, Monterrey, Higher Class].

In this case, it is never questioned whether the practice of using disposable dishes represents either costs or benefits in terms of money, time, convenience, or ecological welfare. Rather, it is a habit that is repeated across generations and transferred from one generation to the next. In other cases, traditional daily routines are maintained by consumers belonging principally to the bottom of the pyramid. For example, whereas the use of plastic bags given for free at retailers is proliferating, some families from lower classes maintain the practice of bringing their own bag to the store. However, these habits are not based so much on a strong conviction regarding environmental protection; instead, they are rooted in heritage and tradition. This is indeed true for several other environmental practices of the lower class, such as collecting paper.

It is striking that some environmentally-problematic behaviors, such as the use of disposable dishes, seem to permeate even to the most modest income groups in the Mexican society. Many of these very-low income groups at the bottom of the pyramid live virtually from one day to the next, not knowing whether they will have enough food for the weeks to come. However, using disposable dishes has become increasingly popular among these families. Unfortunately, it is the proliferation of these symbols of modernity that often replaces previous environmentally-friendly practices. Environmentally-friendly behaviors, especially those performed by the lower social classes, experience a constant tension in terms of the maintenance of habits and traditions on one hand, and modernity, progress, and change on the other hand. We argue that if previous environmentally-friendly practices were ingrained in a more solid and conscious basement of environmental knowledge, modern environmentally-problematic behaviors would not as easily permeate into all strata of Mexican society.

Discussion and managerial implications

Overall, this study contributes to a better understanding of the motivators and inhibitors of environmentally-friendly consumer behavior in emerging economies. By showing that the main factors influencing green behaviors are centered on the three themes of consumer confusion, trust, and credibility, policy makers and marketing practitioners can adapt their regulative actions, marketing offers, and communications accordingly. Our study demonstrates that although environmental behaviors may be similar for different social strata in an emerging economy, the underlying motivations can be very different. The absence of knowledge and education about environmental issues is persistent, especially among the lower social classes. However, even the more educated informants in our study expressed major doubts when discussing what environmentally-friendly behavior or green products really mean. In some cases, respondents claimed outright that companies and the media intentionally misinform consumers and lie about the implications and benefits of eco-friendly products. It

seems that media communication from private and public organizations have not contributed substantially to the increase in consumers' knowledge on environmental matters. Some consumers also seem to be suspicious of the Janus face discourses of governments from industrialized countries and their multinational enterprises, which promise progress but deliver social inequalities and environmental degradation (Eden and Lenway, 2001). This issue presents an opportunity to shift communication strategy towards a more effective approach. Consumer packaged goods companies, retailers, and the government need to collaborate to explain the practical benefits of green products and improve packaging and labels in order to facilitate comprehension and avoid consumer confusion. It is also evident that there is a need to develop transparent industry standards and certification processes. Hence, institutions and businesses should try to establish trustful relationships and thus allow marketers of green products to build a congruent message to attract consumers. Another persistent theme that emerged in our study was price sensibility, especially in the case of families from lower classes. Our results confirm that low income families cannot afford to buy environmentally friendly products if these are significantly more expensive than their "conventional" counterparts. This finding is congruent with the results from previous studies conducted in emerging markets, such as China and India (Chan, 1999; Chan and Lau, 2000; Manaktola and Jauhari, 2007).

Concerning ecologically-friendly (green) products, organizations face a two-fold challenge. On the one hand, marketers may offer the middle and higher social classes in emerging economies green consumer products that have a higher price because of specific benefits, such as containing less toxic substances. These companies should concentrate their positioning efforts on the positive effects of these benefits and create brand differentiation in eco-friendly segments of the market that are willing to pay higher prices for these types of products (Laroche *et al.*, 2001). On the other hand, in the low-income segments of the market, the challenge is to provide affordable eco-friendly alternatives that can lead to family savings. This may be achieved through focusing on products with low-cost manufacturing processes that utilize recyclable or reused materials instead of original materials, dropping middlemen of raw materials supplies (some middlemen dramatically increase the cost of products), and selling directly to clients via agents instead of using cost-ineffective retailers.

Another aspect that appears to inhibit green consumer behavior in Mexico and similar emerging countries relates to modernity. Green practices have not been around for a long time in these regions and technological, social, and economic changes have led consumers to adopt new products that reflect progress and modernity, although these products are, in the majority of cases, not environmentally friendly. This way, the challenge is to construct modernity along with ecological responsibility. It is our

understanding that substantial improvement in the field of changing consumer habits can only be achieved by integrating efforts from consumers, the media, the private sector, and the government. Among these four parties, the latter seems to merit special attention. Most respondents felt that the government should take a more proactive role when it comes to environmental protection, be it by enforcing environmental regulations more strictly or by providing the necessary infrastructure related to public transportation and separation of waste.

Limitations and future research

Because this study is based on a relatively small, qualitative sample of families in an emerging economy, the results may not be representative of either less developed countries on the one hand or industrialized and high-tech economies on the other hand. However, because emerging economies usually have relatively high growth rates accompanied by a rapid degradation of the natural environment, our research may point to problem areas where high levels of improvement can be obtained with relatively few input of monetary resources. Further, our respondents all live in relatively populated urban areas of Mexico, and we did not analyze consumer behavior in more rural regions of the country. Because a substantial portion of consumers in emerging countries such as Mexico, India, or China live on the countryside, future research may explicitly address green consumer behavior in these countries' rural areas. Further, given the fact that consumers associate products labeled as "eco-friendly" with high prices, it might be beneficial to investigate whether lower prices would be enough to increase purchase intentions and actual purchases of green products.

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Executive summary and implications for managers and executives

This summary has been provided to allow managers and executives a rapid appreciation of the content of this article. Those with a particular interest in the topic covered may then read the article in toto to take advantage of the more comprehensive description of the research undertaken and its results to get the full benefits of the material present.

Concern has grown in recent decades for environmental welfare and it is widely acknowledged that consumers, businesses, institutions and governments must act in an ecologically appropriate manner. But in order for necessary changes to occur, it is important to identify factors which function to encourage or inhibit green behaviors.

Environmentally-responsible behavior is a broad term which has been subject to different conceptualizations. Scholars point out that the various terminologies used indicate the priorities and expectations at that time. From the mid-1980s to the late 1990s, for instance, the emphasis was placed on pro-environmental and ecologically-friendly behaviors. During this time the overwhelming message was that people should individually and collectively perform actions which helped to conserve natural resources and safeguard the environment.

Since that period, sustainability has increasingly become the buzzword. The broader spectrum associated with this term means that the focus extends to the welfare of humans and animals as well as the environment. Sustainability encompasses a wide range of actions and behaviors, some of which relate to energy and water, building and birth control. Reduction in the amount of materials used, reusing objects where possible and recycling materials for future usage are other pro-environmental actions. Carrete et al. suggest another of these so-called “pillars”, namely the purchase of products marked as being ecologically-friendly. Its inclusion is assumed to enable sustainable consumption practices to be ascertained more accurately.

A plethora of studies have identified that various external, internal and situational factors influence the green behavior of consumers. Demographic and psychographic features have been considered in other cases. Research conducted in developed markets suggests that attitude and consumer beliefs are significant predictors of behavior whether toward the environment in general or a specific activity like recycling.

The picture within emerging economies appears more ambiguous. Some scholars have discovered scant commitment to environmental issues fueled by such as poor knowledge, high-costs associated with ecologically-friendly products and skepticism about claims made regarding their green credentials. Even in situations when awareness was evident, the environment was not considered a priority. And where ecological behaviors were practiced, consumers were often found to be motivated by reasons other than environmental concern. Research into the purchase of organic food revealed habit and price considerations to be key behavioral determinants. Evidence did reveal consumers who patronized hotels that adopted green behaviors, although they were unwilling to pay extra for this provision.

Attempts to segment green consumers have used different approaches, focusing on such as socio-demographic, psychographic or geographic variables. Among the assumptions are:

- having grown up with environmental issues in the foreground, younger people are more likely to be sensitive to ecological concerns;
- more highly educated people will have greater understanding of the environment and be more concerned as a result;
- higher earners are likelier to purchase green products, being better placed financially to do so;
- green consumers hold more altruistic values towards both society and the environment; and
- environmental attitudes might differ between urban and rural consumers, depending in some nations on factors like their exposure to pollution.

All these approaches have limitations though. For instance, a popular argument is that socio-demographic characteristics are more reflective of knowledge and attitude rather than actual behavior. Evidence also implies a possibility that some of those holding “ecocentric values” could be motivated more by economic reasons. An example of this scenario is when pro-environmental activity is confined to saving energy and water. With regard to geographical variables, social and economic challenges will frequently be greater priorities for consumers in developing nations.

Certain green behaviors do not involve extra costs, though demand regular effort on the consumer’s behalf. But cost is typically an issue with activities like replacing old inefficient technologies with more updated ones. Again, “values, beliefs, norms and habit strength” influence the decisions that individuals make. The impact of values depends on whether consumers perceive their green behavior will have cost and benefit implications for others, the environment or themselves. In addition to personal relevance, social norms are important. If adoption is not regarded as a norm,

consumers can't gauge its social acceptability level. Availability of information, ability to manage costs and inconveniences and risk perception are other issues known to influence new product adoption.

Previous work had suggested that uncertainties and perceived risks could be barriers to the uptake of new technologies by Mexican consumers. The authors aim to identify their concerns in a study examining Mexican families from three regions of the country. The 15 families represented different social class groups and were observed and interviewed by researchers who spent time with them. Relevant data were obtained about "re-using, recycling, reducing and acquiring" green products.

Preliminary analysis was conducted to identify key themes and codes which encourage or inhibit pro-environmental behaviors. This led to findings that:

- In general, green behavior among Mexican consumers was not high level.
- Reducing and re-using was practiced more frequently than recycling or buying organic food.
- Importance to family well-being appears the key motivator for engaging in an ecological behavior. In contrast, Mexican consumers do not closely relate with less tangible notions of society and the environment.
- Lack of clear information by firms and the government limits consumer understanding of such as organic and sustainable practices. Respondents feel the government should be more proactive in enforcing environmental protection.
- Environmental knowledge is greater among younger family members who are socialized at school. In contrast, adults are not typically exposed to "socialization agents" and are more set in their ways. Children are better equipped to adopt a "more holistic worldview" and are conscious of the wider implications of human behavior.
- Consumers are skeptical and confused about claims of product greenness. Trust in manufacturers and retailers is low as they believe profit is the real incentive. The media's role is equally questioned. Some respondents believe the need exists for regulatory standards and certification processes to increase trust.
- Green behavior was motivated by economical rather than environmental reasons, particularly among lower social classes. Prevailing economic uncertainty also deters higher social groups from buying green products.
- Convention and habit are key drivers of consumer behavior and conflict with modern practices such as eco- friendly activities.

Carrete *et al.* urge collaboration between manufacturers, retailers and the government to improve packaging and labels, and provide a consistent message to better inform consumers about the advantages of using green products. Differentiating the brand is an additional strategy firms can adopt to target higher social classes. Reducing

production costs can help create affordable green products for low income consumers. This could be achieved through reusable materials and direct selling to consumers via agents. The authors also suggest moves to position green behavior so that consumers perceive it as an essential part of modernity. Coordinated input from consumers, the media, private sector organizations and the government is regarded as a means to instigate desired behavioral changes.

Future studies could focus on rural areas within different emerging nations and explore whether lower prices alone would impact on purchase intention and behavior of eco- friendly products.